

Corticospinal and corticoreticulospinal projections have discrete but complementary roles in chronic motor behaviors after stroke

Myriam Taga*, Yoon N. G. Hong*, Charalambos C. Charalambous, Sharmila Raju, Leticia Hayes, Jing Lin, Yian Zhang, Yongzhao Shao, Michael Houston, Yingchun Zhang, Pietro Mazzoni, Jinsook Roh#, Heidi M. Schambra#

Stroke	BIC				FDI			
	Ipsilesional CST		Contralesional CReST		Ipsilesional CST		Contralesional CReST	
	cMEP+	cMEP-	iMEP+	iMEP-	cMEP+	cMEP-	iMEP+	iMEP-
Subject n	6	8	9	5	12	2	13	1
Strength (N)	64.7 (44.9)	42.9 (15.5)	63.6 (30.5)*	31.0 (22.2)	8.4 (5.8)*	2.5 (0.1)	8.2 (6.4)	2.6 (0)
Motor control (%)	94.7 (17.3)	82.0 (19.6)	93.6 (18.3)	83.0 (26.5)	91.9 (16.3)	80.9 (8.7)	89.5 (15.7)	76.6 (0)
Individuation (%)	93.5 (12.6)*	81.7 (17.1)	92.2 (17.9)	85.1 (14.9)	89.6 (13.3)	74.9 (0)	89.0 (16)	74.9 (0)
Healthy	BIC				FDI			
	Ipsilesional CST		Contralesional CReST		Ipsilesional CST		Contralesional CReST	
	cMEP+	cMEP-	iMEP+	iMEP-	cMEP+	cMEP-	iMEP+	iMEP-
Subject n	19	8	14	13	27	0	24	3
Strength (N)	53.7 (35.1)	68.9 (78.2)	61.7 (57.4)	41.7 (39.0)	9.1 (4.5)	--	8.8 (4.7)	9.7 (4)
Motor control (%)	97.9 (4.5)	98.5 (7.1)	98.2 (5.5)	98.5 (4.8)	99.2 (2.5)	--	98.8 (2.6)	99.9 (2.1)
Individuation (%)	95.1 (3.8)	96.5 (4.6)	96.4 (3.4)	94 (3.4)	93.3 (3.4)	--	93.4 (3.6)	92.4 (5.9)

Supplemental Table 2. Pathway connectivity and motor behaviors by subject group and muscle. Median (IQR) behaviors are shown for ipsilesional CST and contralesional CReST. Behaviors are split presence or absence functional pathway connectivity (i.e. cMEP +/- or iMEP+/-). We note that imbalanced group sizes considerably limit powered inference about behavioral differences associated with pathway connectivity, although significant differences within muscle and pathway are noted for historical reference. *p < 0.05